

Research Capabilities of a Technical Higher Education Institution in the Bicol Region, Philippines

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Abstract:- Research is an integral part of the Higher Education (HEI) and its impact is undeniably affected by how researchers are capable of undertaking the rigorous process. Relative to this, the study assessed the research capabilities of tertiary education faculty in a rural community in Bicol Region, Philippines through descriptive survey method deployed to 22 faculty members of the Camarines Norte State College – College of Trades and Technology through a survey questionnaire during the 2nd Semester, A.Y. 2022-2023. The results of the data reflect that although the research capabilities of the faculty members are at a mean of 3.0 equivalent to moderately capable, the demographic profile of the faculty members, the bulk of load due to multiple designations as well as the weak impact of expectation of the faculty as a researcher result in the low level of research outputs and undertakings of the College for the past three years. It was also noted that using t-Test at a confidence level of 0.05 shows that the capabilities of BSIT and BTVTED faculty are significantly different. Thus, their improvements are not affected by the other. As a recommendation, it was suggested for the college to investigate the underlying issues at hand to improve the qualifications of the faculty as well as continuously provide research activities that will hone, develop, encourage and expose the faculty members in research activities for improvement of the research services of the college as well as their own personal career growth and development.

Keywords:- Education, research capabilities, descriptive research, research culture, Bicol, Philippines.

I. INTRODUCTION

Camarines Norte State College, with its vision to be a premier higher education institution in Bicol Region is complying with the lacking requirements as prescribed by Commission on Higher Education (CHED), CHTE on its quest to acquire the university status this 2022. The CHED mandates faculty members of higher education institutions (HEIs) to perform its four-fold functions such as instruction, research, extension and community involvement and production. Research services deal with the new knowledge to be contributed to literature and its outputs should be extended to the community. For faculty members, it requires novelty and ingenuity in terms of coming up with research which is novel and can be extended to the beneficiaries of extension.

The faculty members of HEIs are well-aware of their four-fold functions evident with research submissions, completion, presentation, and publication initiatives. However, not all are inclined to technical writing and presentations. Fernandez et al. (2019) found out that faculty members' attitude towards research is high, which means that they have positive opinion although they have reservations because of lack of experiences, they still perceived that they can do research. In addition, the more research experience, the more research engagements are expected from them.

Similarly, Kashani et al. (2021) showed that dimensions of professional empowerment include trust building, team building, knowledge, communication, and organizational culture. Also, global alignment indicators are research dimension, educational dimension, article research dimension, international conferences, and international reputation dimension.

Research capabilities means an individual's facility to undertake high quality studies (Salom, 2013). It develops as he or she continues to undertake research. Given the mandatory function of research for Assistant Professor I and above, there are expectations and targets that need to be fulfilled by these faculty members with these academic ranks. It affects their performances and accomplishments as it is one of the major criteria of evaluating their contributions to the college's targets.

Based on records of the CNSC OVPRE, as of June 30, 2022, for COTT, there are only 7 out of 21 faculty members considered involved in research activities. This figure still falls short in terms of the required number of faculty members engagement considering that the college is gearing towards various levels of AACCUUP Accreditations and conversion to university this 2023. Relatively, publication among faculty members is at 0% although a few faculty members had already submitted articles for publication both for local journal (CNSC Research Journal) and peer reviewed journals beyond the bounds of CNSC. Although all the faculty members with academic rank of Assistant Professor and above are involved in research activities, only 2 had actively submitted completed research for the past years. The college still lacks publication in ISI/Scopus-Indexed or ASEAN Citation Indexed journals. It shows that there is a need to strengthen the research capabilities of the faculty members to be able to comply with changing academic community.

Considering the current statistics of faculty members researchers in the locale of the study, it is therefore the high of time to conduct research which investigates the underlying reasons for attaining such number of responsive researchers to one of the mandates of HEIs faculty members which is to perform research function. Consequently, these undertaking results to designing a capacity building program which concretely fits the needs of the CNSC faculty members, hence this collaborative research which considers building gender-diverse teams to help to ensure a broader range of perspectives, which can boost creativity and innovation – and thus research quality. Furthermore, teams with a balanced gender composition from different delivery units of CNSC can perform better and exhibit a more efficient dynamics and productivity, as evidenced by higher shares of publications and citations and broader dissemination to public audiences of collaborative research consist of both genders. Ensuring

diversity in work teams (in terms of gender, age and field of expertise necessitates a clear commitment to promoting gender equality with an intersectional focus; this will create an inclusive organization and promote gender equality in research organizations and higher education institutions, which has a positive impact on inclusiveness and community.

II. FRAMEWORK OF THE STUDY

The research is anchored into the input-process-output model. The input includes variables sch as the profile of the respondents, level of research capabilities of the faculty members, factors affecting the conduct of research activities and expectations of faculty on their research function. The output is the capacity development activities designed to strengthen the research capabilities of the faculty members of the college:

Fig. 1: Framework of the study

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

This research utilized descriptive survey method in determining the research capabilities of the College of Trades and Technology faculty members. It sought to identify the profile of the respondents, assess the level of research capabilities of along the identified areas of research process, identify the factors affecting the respondents in conducting research activities and determine the expectations of faculty on their research function in the HEI. It also employed appreciative inquiry in interpreting the data gathered from the investigation.

B. Population

The population of the study includes all plantilla faculty members in the College of Trades and Technology for the 2nd Semester, A.Y. 2022-2023. Specifically, these are faculty members with both permanent and temporary appointment as they are the ones that are considered to take course of actions along the four-fold functions of an HEI

along research, extension, production, and instruction. Contract of Service Faculty members were not included as it was clearly stipulated in their contracts that they are only to accomplish tasks under instruction and that they are paid per the teaching service they rendered to the clientele of the College.

C. Data Collection and Instrument

A survey questionnaire developed using google forms was utilized to get the necessary data from the research respondents. This was used to gather relevant information particularly the research capabilities of faculty members of the College of Trades and Technology. Part I consists of the profile of the respondents in terms of academic rank, major field of expertise, number of years in service, research classification based on CHed guidelines, number of research-related trainings/seminars participated in the last three years, number of completed research in the last three years, and research undertakings. Part II consists of the assessment on the level of research capabilities of respondents along the identified areas of research process

such as preparation of capsule proposal, preparation of full-blown proposal, data gathering, preparation of terminal report, presentation of research, and publication of research output. Part III consists of the identification of the factors affecting the respondents in conducting research activities. Lastly, Part IV consists of the expectations of the faculty on their research function.

The survey questionnaire was forwarded to the respondents through links on any available platforms which was not limited to FB Messenger accounts and e-mail addresses of the target respondents. Also, an informed consent was attached to the survey questionnaire to secure approval and to ensure that the respondents are aware of the proceedings of the any information derived from the said survey.

D. Data Analysis

The data coming from the respondents were gathered, tabulated, computed, and analyzed. Frequency and percentage were used to describe the profile of the respondents as well as to disclose the expectations of faculty members on their research functions. Weighted mean was utilized to assess the level of research capabilities of the respondents along the identified areas of research process, while ranking was used to determine the factors affecting the respondents in conducting research activities. Finally, paired T-Test was utilized to determine significant difference between the capabilities of the faculty members from the two departments of the College: Industrial Technology Department and the Technical-Vocational Teacher Education Department.

E. Ethical Protocols

To follow the standard ethics procedure, the researchers sought the approval of the Human Resource Management Officer of the College through letter request for permission to conduct data gathering. An informed consent form was also provided to the faculty members which signifies their willingness to take part in the study as respondents.

The results was treated with utmost confidentiality as mandated by the Data Privacy Act of 2012 and the Manual of Operations of the Research Services.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Upon consolidation of the results, 100% retrieval rate was accounted from the plantilla faculty of the College of Trades and Technology. This is equivalent to twenty-two (22) faculty members, where fifteen (15) are temporary and seven (7) are permanent.

Data collected along the Demographic Profiles of the respondents shows that majority of the faculty members are at the Instructor rank. This constitutes to 73% of the total plantilla faculty whereas, only 1 out of 22 belongs to the Associate Professor rank which is the highest rank a faculty in the College attained. This may be attributed to the compliance to minimum requirements of the Commission on Higher Education for faculty teaching in the tertiary

level where a Master's degree relevant to the field of their baccalaureate must be obtained to secure permanent position as well as eligibility for promotion as stipulated in CHED-DBM Joint Circular No. 3, series of 2022.

In terms of their positions, it was also noted that 21 out of 22 respondents are designees either in local as given by the Director of the campus or in the systemwide where the College President duly signs the document. On the other hand, since the College is a technical school that offers technology programs along industrial and teacher education, it can be noted that majority of the faculty are along technology and science areas. This includes the field of electrical technology, automotive technology, garments technology, food trades, electronics technology, computer technology mathematics, and physics and sciences. This is equivalent to 14 out of 22 faculty or 63.63%. Relative to this, the remaining faculty members belongs to language and panitikan, and physical education to complement the curricular program.

When it comes to the length of service, since most of the faculty are in the Instructor rank, it only aligns that the 68% of the faculty members are in the early stage of their teaching career which is below 10 years of service. On the other hand, with the senior faculty in the College already establishing themselves in the teaching profession, only 32% are within this length of service. Relative to this, it was also noted that no one qualified to the researcher classification among the faculty. The European Research Career Framework (2011) was adopted to determine the broad profile of the faculty along research. This includes First Stage Researcher who are doctoral candidates conducting research under the supervision of a principal investigator in the industry or in the College, Early Career Researcher or Recognized Researcher who are PhD holder who were not yet established the significant independence in terms of research, Established Researcher who have already had a degree of independence in conducting research studies, and finally, Leading Researchers who are already experts in the field of research and oftentimes, lead a group of researchers for a Research and Development endeavor. The results shows that the college lacks anyone who could be classified among the four. This may be attributed to the on-going compliance to graduate and post graduate degree of the faculty members which makes them unqualified to be profiled among the four.

On a positive note, relevant data also shows that engagement and involvement in research activities were still considered and participated in by faculty members. 77% of the faculty members all agreed to have at least attended and participated in research trainings, seminars, fora, and conferences for the last three years. while only 14% claimed that they had not attended any activities related to research. Relatively, 32% of the faculty members also claimed to have completed at least 1 to 3 research studies for the last three years. Although these statistics is significantly low compared to those who had not conducted any research at all, all of this may be connected to different elements.

Table 1: Demographic Profile of the Respondents (N = 22)

Characteristics		Frequency	Percentage
<i>Academic rank</i>			
	Instructor I - III	16	73%
	Assistant Professor I - IV	5	23%
	Associate Professor I - V	1	5%
	Professor I - VI	0	0%
<i>Position</i>			
	Local Designee	13	59%
	Systemwide Designee	8	36%
	No Designation	1	5%
<i>Major Field of Specialization</i>			
	Electrical Technology	1	5%
	Automotive Technology	1	5%
	Garments Technology	2	9%
	Food Trades	3	14%
	Electronics Technology	2	9%
	Computer Technology	1	5%
	English Language	2	9%
	Physical Education	2	9%
	Mathematics	2	9%
	Filipino	2	9%
	Physics/Sciences	2	9%
	Others	0	0%
<i>Number of Years in Service</i>			
	Less than one year	0	0%
	1 - 5 years	10	45%
	6 - 10 years	5	23%
	11 - 15 years	4	18%
	16 - 20 years	0	0%
	21 years and above	3	14%
<i>Research classification</i>			
	First Stage	0	0%
	Early Career	0	0%
	Established	0	0%
	Leading Researcher	0	0%
	None of the Above	21	100%
<i>Number of research-related trainings and seminars participated in the last three years</i>			
	None	3	14%
	1 - 5	16	73%
	6 - 10	3	14%
	11 - 15	0	0%
	16 and above	0	0%

Research undertakings are activities that are related to the conduct of research studies. This may be considered internally which is institutional base, or externally which means that the conduct of studies is sponsored or may be

collaborated with other research institutions, academes, or relevant agencies in need of assistance. Table 2 below reflects the undertakings of faculty members in along research in the last three years:

Table 2: Research Undertaking for the Last Three Years (N = 22)

Particulars	Internal		External	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
<i>Number of Technically evaluated research proposals</i>				
None	3	14%	22	100%
1 - 3	18	82%	0	0%
4 - 6	1	5%	0	0%
7 - 9	0	0%	0	0%
10 and above	0	0%	0	0%
<i>Number of on-going researches with MOA</i>				
None	11	50%	22	100%
1 - 3	11	50%	0	0%
4 - 6	0	0%	0	0%
7 - 9	0	0%	0	0%
10 and above	0	0%	0	0%
<i>Number of completed researches</i>				
None	15	68%	22	100%
1 - 3	6	27%	0	0%
4 - 6	1	5%	0	0%
7 - 9	0	0%	0	0%
10 and above	0	0%	0	0%

Table 2 reflects that no endeavors was conducted for external research, however, institutional research activities were noted in the table presented. In terms of technical evaluation of research proposals, statistics reflect that 82% of the faculty members had already subjected their research proposals, be it collaborative or sole authorship, for technical evaluation. This process is the review of the technicalities and the eligibility of the proposed study for funding in the institution. Relatively, out of said figure, 11 faculty members have on-going researches with approved

and notarized Memorandum of Agreement with the institution. This legally binds the researcher with the CNSC as the funding agency as well as intellectual properties that may be generated in the course of the study. On the other hand, only 27% of the faculty had their studies completed in the last three years. With these figures, it can be noted in Table 3 that no research articles were published in high impact journals as indexed by Scopus, ISI or Thompson Reuters. Only where able to submit their completed research for publication to the local journal in CNSC.

Table 3: Research Publications for the Last Three Years (N = 22)

Particulars	Local/CHED Refereed Journals		Scopus/ISI/Thompson Reuters	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
<i>Number of Published Researches</i>				
None	19	86%	22	100%
1 - 3	3	14%	0	0%
4 - 6	0	0%	0	0%
7 - 9	0	0%	0	0%
10 and above	0	0%	0	0%

Research endeavors may be subdivided in to seven stages. Each stages reflect significant areas that each of the researchers practice and hone to ensure high level competence and to enhance their skills in technical writing and research presentations. As such, level of research capabilities of the faculty members were measured along the preparation of capsule proposals, preparation of full-

blown proposals, data gathering, preparation of terminal reports, presentation of research studies in either local, regional, national or international conferences and fora, and publication of research output in indexed and refereed journals. Table 3 reflects the results of the assessment conducted among the faculty of the College of Trades and Technology:

Table 4: Level of Research Capabilities along the identified Areas of Research Process (N = 22)

Particulars		Weighted Mean	Rounded Equivalent	Adjectival interpretation
<i>Preparation of Capsule Proposal</i>				
	Preparing introduction	3.32	3	Moderately Capable
	Preparing Literature Review	3.23	3	Moderately Capable
	Preparing Conceptual Framework	3.09	3	Moderately Capable
	Preparing Theoretical Framework	2.91	3	Moderately Capable
	Preparing Statement of the Problem/Objectives of the Study	3.27	3	Moderately Capable
	Preparing Methodology	3.09	3	Moderately Capable
<i>Preparing Full-Blown Proposal</i>				
	Preparing Compliance to recommendations	3.09	3	Moderately Capable
	Preparing Survey Questionnaire contents	2.95	3	Moderately Capable
	References using APA or other required citation	3.14	3	Moderately Capable
	Budgetary requirements	3.14	3	Moderately Capable
	Dry-run	2.95	3	Moderately Capable
<i>Data Gathering</i>				
	Preparing survey questionnaire using google form	3.32	3	Moderately Capable
	Distributing survey questionnaire in hard copies	3.36	3	Moderately Capable
	Seeking approval of research respondents	3.18	3	Moderately Capable
	Seeking approval of concerned agency/ies	3.09	3	Moderately Capable
	Making schedules of follow-ups	3.18	3	Moderately Capable
	Preparing the statistical reports	2.82	3	Moderately Capable
<i>Preparation of Terminal Report</i>				
	Abstract	3.00	3	Moderately Capable
	Textual presentations	3.00	3	Moderately Capable
	Writing implications/interpretation of results	2.82	3	Moderately Capable
	Providing basis for claims	2.82	3	Moderately Capable
	Making output/s based from the result of the study	2.86	3	Moderately Capable
	Making findings and conclusions	2.91	3	Moderately Capable
	Providing recommendations	2.86	3	Moderately Capable
<i>Presentation of Research (local/regional/national/international)</i>				
	Searching for conferences/fora to present research	2.59	3	Moderately Capable
	Complying with institution's requirements for possible funding and support	2.68	3	Moderately Capable
	Complying with format based on the guidelines of the organizing institution	2.77	3	Moderately Capable
	Delivery of presentation in Zoom/online	2.77	3	Moderately Capable
	Delivery of presentation in F2F	2.77	3	Moderately Capable
<i>Publication of Research Output</i>				
	Searching for valid journals for possible publication	2.50	3	Moderately Capable
	Passing the plagiarism test	2.68	3	Moderately Capable
	Complying with format based on the guidelines of the journal	2.64	3	Moderately Capable
	Fulfilling the suggestions or recommendations during peer review	2.68	3	Moderately Capable
	Conforming the timelines of submission of completed papers	2.45	2	Somewhat Capable

The result of the assessment reflects that the general notion as to the capability of the faculty members in the stages of research endeavors is moderately capable. This enunciates that along the seven stages of the conduct of

research, they can deliver what is required for each stage. However, upon evaluation of the result, it was also noted that in terms of conforming to the timelines of submission of complete papers under Publication of Research Output,

the mean score only reached 2.45 or equivalent to Somewhat Capable. It can be gleaned that certain factors affects the time management of faculty members when it comes to documenting and complying with the comments for completed research outputs.

Furthermore, using t-Test for the paired Two Sample Means of BSIT and BTVTED capabilities in conducting

research studies at a level of confidence ($\alpha = 0.05$), the results reflect that the p-value of 0.009643969 is less than the confidence level. Thus, it further implies that there is a significant difference between the means of the BSIT and BTVTED faculty along their capabilities in conducting research studies.

Table 5: t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means

	BSIT	BTVTED
Mean	3	3.277777778
Variance	0.04	0.021296296
Observations	6	6
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	5	
t Stat	-4.068942294	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.004821985	
t Critical one-tail	2.015048373	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.009643969	
t Critical two-tail	2.570581836	

Along the research undertaking as well as involvement of CoTT Faculty in terms of research, it was noted that several areas are weak. Relatively, Table 6

reflects the factors that may have influenced their drive to conduct research studies:

Table 6: Factors Affecting the Respondents in Conducting Research Activities (N = 22)

Parameters	Frequency Count	Rank
Multi-designation/additional workloads	15	2nd
Inadequate knowledge in conducting research	9	5th
Time constraints/lack of time to do research	19	1st
Heavy teaching loads	7	7th
Lack of financial support from institution	2	10th
Personal issues	10	3rd
Limited experience on data collection methods	10	3rd
Lack of previous studies in the research area	5	9th
Difficulty in coming up with possible research titles	7	7th
Insufficient Skills in data analysis	8	6th

The table reflects that the most prevailing factor identified by the respondents is the time constraints or lack of time to do research studies. A total count of 19 was consolidated. This notion was backed up by the next in rank in the table which is multi-designation and additional workload. It can be gleaned that due to the bulk of work carried out by the faculty in their respective designation as well as the duty as a faculty to teach under instruction, there is not enough time left for them to conduct or get involved in research studies. It was also noted that personal issues as well as limited experience on data collection methods were identified as ranked 3rd of the most prevailing factors that affects the faculty in the conduct of research.

On the contrary, the lack of financial support from the institution was noted to be the least prevailing factor in the conduct of research as the institution ensures the proper allocation per each college for research services is observed as mandated in CHED Memorandum Order No. 20, series of 2010 where a 10% allocation from the income fund of the college must be allotted for research.

Also, to determine among the faculty members their expectation in their research function, Table 7 summarizes their responses:

Table 7: Expectations of Faculty Members on their Research Function (N = 22)

Parameters	Frequency Count	Rank
To participate in continuing education programs on research organized by the college	16	2nd
To engage in multidisciplinary /collaborative researches	15	3rd
To instruct/guide students' projects	7	6th
To collaborate with other teachers/faculty including other colleges	17	1st
To observe students during their practicum week	5	9th
To participate in research conferences (even if not presenting)	15	3rd
To publish refereed articles	3	10th
To initiate research projects	0	19th
To present research at local/regional/national/international research conferences	7	6th
To represent the college in research collaborations	1	17th
To contribute new generated knowledge for the benefit of the community	8	5th
To write and develop research program/projects	7	6th
To publish policy papers or research reports	1	17th
To receive invitations on research lectures and conferences	3	10th
To present at international conferences	0	19th
To present studies (his/her or others') at faculty meetings	3	10th
To submit requests for internal and external research funds	2	16th
To submit a solo research on the field of specialization	3	10th
To increase number article citations	3	10th
To be a research paper reviewer in an international/Scopus index/ISI/CHEd accredited journal	3	10th

Based from the data collected, it was noted that most of the faculty are aware that as a faculty with research function, they are to do collaborate with other teachers and faculty including other colleges to conduct research. This notion ranked 1st among the list which goes in line with the trend on multi-disciplinary research activities along the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations. They expect to participate in continuing education programs on research organized by the college or by other relevant agencies to ensure that their professional growth and skills in writing research articles mainstreamed and honed. This notion ranked 2nd in the list with a total of 16 counts of agreement. In addition, they also believe that they are to engage in multidisciplinary or collaborative research activities as well as participate in research conferences to expand their horizon when it comes to research. This ranked 3rd at a total frequency count of 15.

On the contrary, it was also noted that they do not expect to initiate research projects, present at international conferences, represent the college in collaborative research, and to be able to publish policy papers or research reports. Which was ranked least among the identified expectations.

The results of expectations may be attributed to the fact that majority of the faculty members are in the Instructor rank where they are not required to conduct research. Furthermore, this also gleans that the idea of professional growth through research is not in their mind as the notion seem to strike them with difficulties along several areas as identified in Table 6

V. CONCLUSION

Based from the forgoing facts presented in the discussion, the following conclusions were drawn: the demographic profile of the respondents particularly the academic rank heavily affects the research engagement and endeavors of the faculty members in the College of Trades and Technology as most of the faculty are in the Instructor I rank, had served less than 10 years in the service, and had not yet completed a relevant Master's degree in line with their field of expertise. Thus, these results to not being profiled to any of the four (4) stages of researchers from the European Research Career Framework. This also results to low level of research undertaking for the last three years from research completed, paper presentation, and finally, publications. Although, the capabilities of the faculty along the seven (7) stages of the conduct of research reflects that all are moderately capable of conducting a study, however, it can be noted that they are somewhat capable of complying with the due date of submitting research outputs as scheduled. Furthermore, it was noted that there is also a significant difference between the capabilities of the BSIT and BTVTED faculty as statistics shows that the mean of BTVTED faculty members is slightly higher than that of the BSIT faculty. This maybe attributed to the fact that majority of the faculty are heavily load with workloads due to their multi-designations as well as their duty as a faculty member under instruction. This results to an unmanaged time and insufficient time to conduct research studies that will benefit the College. Finally, these facts sums up to the expectation of the faculty members which also reflects a weak understanding of their role as a researcher in the College. It shows that they do not expect to initiate research projects, present at international conferences, represent the college in collaborative research, and to be able to publish policy papers or research reports. Which was ranked least

among the identified expectations. This mindset reflects a low level of apprehension as to their professional growth in the academe as one of the mandates of CNSC is research and development.

VI. TRANSLATIONAL RESEARCH

With these conclusions drawn, the following were considered: the college consider revisited the faculty profile and determine underlying issues as to why the educational qualifications of the faculty had not been met as it greatly affects the research endeavors and strength of the research services of the College. Furthermore, the college continuously provided activities that will hone and encourage faculty to conduct research along their field of specialization to improve the research undertaking and involvement of the College. Especially as to the fundamentals of technology research along the research agenda of the Institution. This include trainings and workshops as well as mentoring and coaching. In addition, the institution also revisited the designations of all faculty members and determined underlying issues as to why is there overlapping designations that hinders productivity among faculty members. Evenly distributing duties among the faculty members including teaching loads would ensure improvement towards research undertakings and outputs. Finally, the college considered conducting peer mentoring and collaborative researches within and beyond the college to encourage the faculty in conducting research as well as change their mindset to a more productive one.

The role of research is not just to develop the community through technology development and innovation, but also to develop individual's professional career.

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